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KHALIDE EDIB ADIVAR AND “THE ORDEAL”

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ХАЛИДЕ ЭДИБ АДЫВАР И «ИСПЫТАНИЕ»

Abstract.

One of the immortal works by Khalide Edib Adivar “The ordeal” (1922), written during the National Literature period, reflects with deep sensitivity the important role played in the lives of various people in society during the War of Independence and the National Struggle period (1918-1922), in which she also participated. In this article it is said about the theme of the literary example, the characters and the idea that wanted to transmit to society. One can call this work not just a war, but also a psychological novel, in which love for the native land, a story of self-sacrifice and resistance, pure feelings of love are reflected.

Аннотация.

Одно из бессмертных произведений Халиде Эдип Адывар — роман «Испытание» (1922), написанный в период Национальной Литературы, с глубокой чувствительностью отражает важную роль, которую сыграла в жизни различных слоёв общества. война за независимость и период национально-освободительной борьбы (1918–1922), в которой она сама принимала участие. В статье рассматриваются тема данного литературного произведения, его персонажи и идея, которую автор стремилась донести до общества. Это произведение можно назвать не только военным, но и психологическим романом, в котором отражены любовь к родной земле, история самопожертвования и сопротивления, а также чистые чувства любви.

Keywords: War of Independence, Izmir, Greek, occupation, native land, fire

Ключевые слова: Война за независимость, Измир, греки, оккупация, родная земля, огонь.

Introduction

One of the powerful figures who brought a new breath to the Turkish literature and prose of the 20th century with her rich and multifaceted creativity, at the same time played an important role in the formation of the literary taste of this period and gave a strong impetus to the generation that came after her is Khalide Edib Adivar. The period when she began her career coincided with the fateful, significant historical changes in society in Turkey. The early period of the master’s creativity falls on the period of “Wealth of knowledge”, the middle period falls on the period of National Literature and later on the period of the Republic. The master wrote novels, stories, plays and memoirs, all of which are valuable and reflect the problems of her time.

Khalide khanim has a significant place and position in 20th century Turkish literature and has gained more fame in the literary space with her prose examples such as “Grocery store with flies”, “The ordeal”, “New Turan”, “Handan”, “Zeyno’s son”, “Tatar”, etc., and has gained deep love and sympathy from a wide audience.

Investigation

The themes addressed in the works of this powerful master, who began her creative career during the proclamation of the Second Constitutional Monarchy (1908), were mainly the involvement of women in science and education in the early years and the protection

of their rights, later, during the years of the War of Independence, she wrote novels that appealed to the heroic Turkish people to unite against the enemy, to be together and to further increase their feelings of patriotism.

In general, Khalide Edip Adivar’s activity is multifaceted and the main themes of her works are mainly her turbulent life, period and historical moments. Looking through her biography, one can see that the reason she addresses political issues more often stems from her personal life. Her father, Mehmed Edib Bey, was an oppositional-minded bureaucrat who handled financial affairs in the sultan’s treasury at the palace of Abdulhamid II. Khalide Edib was born in Beshiiktash and completed her education at the Uskudar American College for Girls, becoming one of the first Muslim women to graduate from that institution. Her politically developing ideas were largely formed during her years at this college and her studies with feminist teachers also had a significant impact on shaping her worldview.

In the early years of her activity she was threatened at some points because her literary examples promoted ideas such as women’s rights, their role in society and their involvement in education, in general, Khalide Edib’s life has been so tumultuous that it even overshadows her novels. Her first husband, Salih Zeki, was an intellectual, a prominent mathematician and philosopher of his time and had been Khalide khani’s

teacher and of course, he was older than her. This marriage covers an important period of her life and according to the researchers' thoughts, it is known that her novel "Handan" also includes some moments from her own life. Khalide khanim began her creative work mainly after the proclamation of the Second Constitutional Monarchy, i.e., in 1908. Despite her young age, she had already developed a very strong character (perhaps the many events in her personal life laid the foundation for it). The moral and psychological trauma she experienced during her first marriage (1901-1911) affected her works, especially the work "Handan". If Khalide khanim glorified female freedom, tender feelings of love and secret feelings of affection in this work, the novel "The ordeal" (1922), which will be discussed below, glorifies the heroism of Turkish woman.

With this novel, which tells the story of the national struggle and the Turkish War of Independence in Turkey, the powerful master Khalide Edib Adivar created a unique example of the National Literature Era. This work is considered the first prose work written in Turkey on the subject of the War of Independence and is still considered one of the best novels ever written. The prose sample reflects both Khalide khanim's love for Anatolia and at the same time the manifestation of her nationalist ideology ignited by the War of Independence. This novel was written at the time when significant events occurred in Turkish society after World War I, the successive occupations of Istanbul and Izmir, and as a result, the feeling of protecting the native land was ignited in every citizen and the war continued. Since June 1922, that work had been published in parts in the newspaper "Ikdam" and presented to the public. The work consists of the fragile memories of Peyami, a foreign affairs officer, written in his own words while waiting for the day of his surgery in the hospital.

At the beginning of the novel Peyami is described in detail as a Westernized, European-style person, his "A la franga" lifestyle, their house in the district Shishli, where he lives luxuriously with his mother, the daughter of a wealthy family from Izmir who grew up in Istanbul, and the parties held in that house. Peyami refuses to marry his close relative, Aishe, as his mother advised, because he does not consider his "provincial" relatives to be suitable for the society he belongs to. In general, at the beginning of the novel, Peyami, talking about his life, notes that it was lifeless and oppressive, and after meeting the heroes of this story, it seemed that his own life was gaining value. As he noted, this story is more about their life (Aishe and Ehsan) than about his own. The change in his way of looking at life begins after meeting his mother's cousin, officer Jamal, who was wounded several times in the military, his friend Ehsan and other comrades. On the eve, when the British opened fire on Istanbul, they saw the wounded residents of the city, all three young people were tormented and helpless against the oppression of the enemy. With the occupation of Izmir, which is important in the work, the events are directed to a completely different course. Jamal's sister Aishe, her husband Mukbil Bey and their young son are murdered brutally by the Greeks. Aishe herself survived, having been wounded in the arm. After the occupation of Izmir by the Greeks, as reflected

in the work, it is as if an awakening, a panic arises in Istanbul, the Sultanahmet rally, at which Khalide khanim herself participated and which is remembered for her historic speech reflecting the determination, pride and resolve of the Turkish nation, delivered to thousands of her compatriots, has also been described vividly and emotionally. Peyami, Jamal, Ehsan, who were deeply moved by this crowd and felt an awakening within them, and Aishe from Izmir, dressed in black and standing with determination and pride despite all the hardships she faced, are also among this crowd. It was precisely with this proud stance that Aishe, unable to hold back her tears, had already made Peyami fall in love with her.

Jamal, Ehsan and Aishe form the basis of Peyami's penned memories, sincerely admitting that after meeting these heroes, his life acquired a value. This acquaintance causes his patriotic feelings to flare up even more: "Peyami has less life-folk experience than the writer. The people and nature he sees on the road, especially during the National Struggle, deeply affect him. The new world he encounters increasingly distances him from the old Peyami. He describes these impressions, which change him as they come into contact with him, with the excitement of the first, perhaps even the last, encounter" (1, 18). The attack of the Bulgarians on Izmir, the attack of the British on Istanbul, the events taking place in the city were described with great excitement from the hero's language. The controversy of British reporter Mr. Kuk with Aishe at Peyami's house in Shishli again brings to the fore what a patriotic person this brave woman is. The anger and hateful response of Aishe to Mr. Kuk for his offensive remarks about the Turkish nation, the tribulations of the British against this militant people, the disasters that occurred in Izmir are recalled, through the tragic fate of the native land, we relive Aishe's suffering once again, the brutal murder of her husband and child seems to unfold vividly before our eyes.

Later, Aishe, who joined Anatolia as a nurse, is now surrounded by Peyami and Ehsan, both of whom are people from other worlds, and both are in love with Aishe. As Peyami gets to know Aishe, he is amazed at her endurance and steadfastness, but as time goes on, he finds that Ehsan is also deeply in love with Aishe, but keeps his feelings a secret, not letting them down.

In the work, it is symbolic that a number of soldiers, who went to Izmir, on their way kissed Aishe's injured left hand – the daughter of Izmir, as if symbolizing the liberation military. The image of Aishe is a character representing an Anatolian person, a generalized image of thousands of women who have lost their husband, father, brother and children.

In the work the cruel torture of the British in Istanbul is described in Aishe's letters to Peyami, where at the same time we hear the Turkish heart beating violently for his native land, the patriotic woman expresses her feelings in expressions full of sadness.

The headquarters belonging to Ehsan in the war area is in the village of Sarilar. The writer introduces us to other characters from the Anatolian people here, the girl from this village, Kezban, is in love with the hero Ehsan, she loves him sincerely. In the example of a pure

girl, we see brave, courageous and devoted Anatolian girls. Another character in the work, Sergeant Mammad, is in love with Kezban and hates this brave regiment commander because of his unrequited love and Kezban's love for Ehsan. While Ehsan was in an area with several soldiers, Sergeant Mammad surrounded them with his band of bandits. As Peyami was with them, he witnessed all the events, but the army that Kezban informed about arrived in time to save Ehsan and Sergeant Mammad was killed.

After a while, though Peyami parted ways with Ehsan, but he met him again in Sakarya, where he was sent as a translator and photographer. Here, the two friends have their first sincere conversation and Ehsan shares his feelings for Aisha with him, confessing his love, when he was wounded in one of the battles and thought everything was over, Aishe put cold cloths on his forehead and wet his lips, expressing the feelings he felt as he regained consciousness: "I swear, for a moment I see myself surrounded by the sweetest and most eternal white ether and I imagine myself as a man who has died and entered paradise. Yes, I had become a martyr. Martyrdom had taken me to paradise, all the way to Aisha's eyes. Looking into her eyes, I was once again overcome with ecstasy. What a blessed and absolute gratitude this was" (1, 164). In this part of the work Ehsan confesses his love to Aishe, though Aishe reciprocates this love, but as the most important issue at the moment is the liberation of the homeland from the invaders, she cannot respond to this love with the same feelings. Throughout the work, no one doubts that Aishe will die for her holy goal, for Izmir, as if she is preparing herself for it, she is always ready to become a martyr, telling every soldier who closed his eyes, "We send you to Allah, my friend, we'll meet on the road to Izmir" (1, 41). And so it happens, Ehsan and Aishe were heroically martyred in the Izmir war – on the way to Izmir, which is considered an integral part of the Anatolian geography.

In the section "Sakarya days" of Peyami's memoirs he regretfully notes that Aishe was unaware that he had lost his legs for his native land, because in one of the letters Aishe wrote to him that Peyami worked as an officer's lawyer and was far from the war zone, and asked how he could go to Izmir in that case. In this case, Peyami wished that Aishe would see him thrown into the deep part of the battle and lose his legs. One can understand here a point that it is as if Peyami joined the war zone in order to be close to Aishe: "This morning I recalled how my knees, now empty, ached when I received Aishe's last letter, how my heart and hands trembled with anxiety, as a memory etched in my body. There is a pain of a desperate desire within me. Aishe didn't know that I had lost my legs for Izmir. Even now, if a shell explodes on the front lines and my arms and head remain intact, she doesn't know that I'll crawl away" (1, 146).

Peyami conveys to the reader with enthusiastic feelings how the Turkish army soldiers bravely fought on the way to Izmir, their courage and bravery, each of them swore not to sheathe their swords until Izmir was liberated from the occupation (1, 151).

The work "The ordeal" demonstrates the patriotism, pride and determination of the Turkish people in the personality of Peyami, Aishe, Ehsan and others. At the same time, together with the heroes, we seem to travel inch by inch through Anatolian settlements and villages, get acquainted with the character of these people, admire their pure nature.

Professor Inji Engin mentions the following ideas as one of the main features of the novel "The ordeal": "Khalide Edib's personal contact with the Anatolian people during the years of the National Struggle, after she had become acquainted with them in Istanbul before moving to Anatolia, led her to develop a deep admiration for the Anatolian Turks. It was after this novel that Khalide Edib would go on to portray the Anatolian villager, who had not lost his national and noble qualities, in every one of her novels" (20, 219).

Throughout the work, we witness Peyami's spiritual exaltation, in his last memoir, written the day before the operation in Ankara Jabeji hospital, we are surprised in front of his love for Aishe: "My dear Aishe, look, my arms are still strong. I've sworn to fight for Izmir until my very last breath. Wipe the tears from your eyes. If you want, love Ihsan. That poor man loved you very much. For two years, he carried "the ordeal" on his back. Finally, he fell into your arms in Izmir. Isn't that enough happiness for just one person? This "ordeal" will never leave me, even after I die, I will carry it forever. But I love it, that fire, that agony, Aishe. Just give me a little space at your feet and I'll wait for you right there. I want to be worthy for you, Aishe, if you wish, I'll even lie at Ihsan's feet. Isn't he your owner? Aishe, there hasn't been such torment since the world began" (11, 209). Of course, Ehsan and Aishe are heroically martyred for their country. The work ends with a strange ending, Peyami dies during surgery. It is understood that all this is a fabrication created by the impact of the bullet in Peyami's brain: It turns out that there is neither a nurse named Aishe nor a regiment commander named Ehsan. On the other hand, how could the memories written by Peyami with heartache be considered fiction and dreams. At the beginning of the work, Peyami writes in his memory: "What did the doctor say? The bullet in my head is making a ghost in me", but on the other hand he continues so: "In Istanbul I have a mother who is dark-skinned, with a slender face, taut hair and who never seems to age. She also rejected me when I set out on this adventure. Did I say adventure? So, everything that happened to me is true. Maybe not all of it, but what's the harm?" The powerful master leaves it to the reader.

We would like to draw attention to one more issue. In this work Khalide khanim does not show Europe and Western culture as an example, unlike her earlier novels. On the contrary, she notes how the West pursues a colonial policy, openly declares its hatred, especially towards the British, and the Greeks.

When we look at the works she wrote before writing this novel, for example, in the work "Handan" the author mainly talks about the feelings and emotions of her youth, in the work "The promised judgment" she talks about the society in which the author was contemporary and in "The house with purple clusters" and

“The Trial of the Turk with fire” she talks about her own memories. It means the author turns from the chanting of personal feelings to the problems of society. In this work, the heroic daughter of the militant Turkish people in the image of Aishe is portrayed as a proud, brave person who is ready to give her life for her homeland at any time. However, in her earlier work “Handan” she hoped that it would be possible to express the emotions and feelings of women as an independent person.

Conclusion

The novel “The ordeal” is an example of the first prose account of the National War of Independence and Liberation (1919-1922), which was a key stage in Turkish history. As Mehmet Kaplan noted, this war introduced Anatolia, the Anatolian people, their suffering, spirit and character to Turkish writers (7, 158). The image of Aishe is a generalized image of thousands of women in Anatolia who have lost their husbands, fathers, partners and children.

The theme of love, divine love plays an important role in the work and from this point of view the title of the novel was chosen by the author skillfully, that is, here is the personal tragedy of all three heroes, as well as the place in their lives of the war that took place in the military history of the powerful Turkish people, it is at such a moment that they simply mobilize for the motherland, suppressing their love, individual feelings and emotions within themselves, they give up their love to defeat the enemy.

While Aishe and Ehsan are bound to each other by noble feelings, the liberation of their homeland is of greater importance and this noble feeling burns like a fiery shirt worn by the person. In other words, the main reason of the author in this novel is that if a homeland, a land is under the enemy occupation, if the honor and dignity of the people are in danger, the personal feelings, feelings of pure love are in second place.

The country literature, which is one of the important features of the National Literature period, which began to develop during this period, the sense of national certainty, the rediscovery of Anatolia, the whole character of this person, the love of the motherland, joy, sadness, love, excitement, moral and psychological shocks experienced in the turbulent livelihood of life are reflected in the work “The ordeal” by Khalide Edib Adivar.

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